

A Call for Responsible Innovation in Mobile Mental Health: Findings from a Content Analysis and Ethical Review of the Depression App Marketplace

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Background: Mobile mental health has been lauded for its potential to remove barriers and increase access to care. Yet, many ethical concerns have been raised most commonly related to privacy and security, risks and safety, and benefits and evidence. Examples of these issues are evident in content analyses and reviews of publicly available mental health applications, with apps for depression found to lack research evidence and information provided to potential users about the app, safety, and privacy.

Objective: Our research built on previous reviews and analyses to consider the ethical values and issues in mobile mental health with the aim of exploring solutions for greater ethical design and practice. Guided by principlism, professional ethics, and value sensitive design, we conducted a content analysis of the depression app marketplace to determine the ethical issues evident and how these issues reflect ethical values in app design, development, and marketing.

Methods: Search and data collection was performed in Google Play Store (UK) and Apple iTunes (UK) between October to November 2018. Iterative data extraction and coding of variables and values were conducted prior to synthetization of issues and themes.

Results: Search found 353 unique apps for depression. Analysis of these apps uncovered a range of ethical issues including: limited evidence of intervention validity, fidelity, and outcomes; insufficient safeguarding and duty of care; non-multisector development teams; lack of independent certification and regulation; lack of information and transparency for informed user choices; and concerns with privacy, confidentiality, and user permissions. Findings highlighted the presence and absence of ethical values in publicly available apps for depression, with most apps failing to reflect many key values, namely: (Beneficence) benefits, risk minimization; (Nonmaleficence) avoidance of harm, safety and welfare; (Duty) competence, responsibility, standards; (Integrity) transparency, credibility; (Autonomy) informed choice, privacy and confidentiality; (Justice) accessibility, fairness.

Conclusions: Our findings suggest a need for greater ethical value sensitive design in mobile mental health and consideration of potential ethical dilemmas throughout the lifespan of mental health technologies. This is particularly challenging in mobile mental health given its multidisciplinary approach and the range of associated values. This research uniquely captures the complex ethical and value conflicts in mobile mental health in the wild, through the example of the depression app marketplace. When faced with moral overload, designers may prioritize some values over others, such as a focus on increasing accessibility at the expense of safety. We conclude by encouraging a responsible innovation approach to the design of new technologies and demonstrate how this will better meet ethical demands and practice.

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